

Game Education Specific Characteristics of the Activity of Pre-School Children

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Abstract: In the game, all available aspects of the person are activated: the child moves, speaks, perceives, thinks. The game appears as an important means of education. It is said about the unique feature of the game-based educational activity of preschool children.

Key words: preschool education, game education, education, psychologist, ethnographer, psychologist, children.

INTRODUCTION

The game is a manifestation of the human personality, a way of its improvement. As the game occupies a certain place in the life of adults, it is of special importance for children. It is accepted to call him "childhood companion". It is the main content of preschool children's life. It is manifested as a leading activity in an integral relationship with work and education. Most of the serious things that children do are in the form of play. In the game, all available aspects of the person are activated: the child acts, speaks, perceives, thinks. The game appears as an important means of education.

Since ancient times, the game has attracted the attention of pedagogues, psychologists, philosophers, ethnographers, and art historians. Primitive community tribes reflected hunting, war, farming in their games. For example, the process of sowing rice in some tribes at that time was carried out as a huge ceremony with games.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The first stage of children's game activity is an introductory game, which is an object-item-game activity. Its content is complex and delicate movements in handwork.

The next stage is the reflection game. This is the highest point in the development of the psychological content of early childhood play. If adults carry out their educational work with a certain consistency, children of this age will learn the names of objects and objects, what they are used for, and will begin to apply this new knowledge in their games. Children's game of this age reflects object activity in terms of content.

At the end of the first age and at the end of the second age, a plot reflection occurs in children's play. The child demonstrates how to use the object in his hand.

The next stage is a role-playing game, in which children reflect the work and social relations of adults they know.

Scientific ideas about the step-by-step development of children's play activities made it possible to develop specific systematic recommendations for guiding children's play activities in different age groups.

Thus, the role of the game in the pedagogical process of MTT is very large, and the game is widely used in raising and teaching children of preschool age. Because:

- the game is an independent activity of children, in which the psyche of the child is manifested
- will be;
- the game is a form of externalizing the life of preschool children;
- the game is one of the means of comprehensive education of children;
- the game is a method and method of education and upbringing of children;
- the game is a means of preparing children for educational activities.

Researches conducted by well-known pedagogues-scientists have shown that it is possible to influence children's content, externalization, structure, moral relations of children, the level of development of children's play through complex guidance of the game.

The game is a means of development and education of children. Psychologists consider the game to be the leading activity in preschool age. Thanks to the game, qualities are formed that ensure the transition of the child to a higher stage of development, significant changes occur in his psyche.

In the game, all aspects of the child's personality are formed by interacting with each other. By observing a child at play, you can learn about his interests, his perception of his surroundings, and his attitude towards adults and friends. A regular game allows the child to regularly train his sensory development, thinking and speech, involuntary attention and memory, and various movements. Each game with rules has a certain didactic purpose and is aimed at the general development of the child. It is important that education is in the form of a game and is aimed at the general development of the child. It is important that education is in the form of a game, and it corresponds to the age characteristics of the child. An interesting game increases the child's mental activity, in the game the child can solve a more complex problem than in training. This is not to say that education should be entirely in the form of games. Education requires the use of various methods and methods. The game is one of the forms of education, and it gives a good result only when it is combined with other methods, such as observation, conversation, telling, etc.

While playing, the child learns to use his knowledge and to be able to use it in different situations. In creative games, children's imagination, making things, and experimenting open up a wide path.

Along with intellectual development, moral qualities are also formed in the game. Experiences during the game leave a deep impression on the child's mind, so the game helps to develop good feelings, lofty dreams and aspirations, and healthy interests in the child.

The game is an independent activity, during which children begin to communicate with their peers. They are united by a common goal and common ways to achieve it. That is why the game is important in cultivating friendly relations, forming team life skills, and organizational skills. Complex relationships arise in a group of small children united by joint play. The teacher's task is to involve every child in an active game, to establish relationships between children based on friendship, honesty, and a sense of responsibility for their comrades.

The game also helps to fulfill the task of labor education. Children reflect the winters of various professions in their games. With this, they not only imitate the actions of adults, but also reflect their attitude towards their work. The game often awakens the child's desire to work, forces him to prepare and make things necessary for the game. In the game, the interest in technology that is characteristic of modern children appears and develops, children make various machines and play with technical toys.

The game is an important tool of aesthetic education. Creative imagination and thinking skills arise and develop in the game. A well-chosen toy helps to develop artistic taste. Children are fascinated by the beauty and rhythm of action in action games. The great educational value of the game is not realized by

itself. The game can be useless, even harmful, and sometimes it can cause bad feelings. In order to carry out the task of all-round development of children with the help of the game, the educator needs to influence him regularly.

CONCLUSION

In solving this task, the game should be connected with all aspects of educational work in kindergarten. In the game, the knowledge and skills acquired by the children during the training are reflected and developed, and through them the child is taught about life. On the other hand, qualities cultivated in the game are transferred to other types of activity.

Used literature

1. Abdurazzoqova Z., Mamatova M. Darslarda yangi ilg'or texnologiyaning qo'llanilishi // Ta'lim texnologiyalari; 2007 yil 1-soni.
2. Avliyakov N.H., Musayeva N.N. Pedagogik texnologiyalar. -T: "Fan va texnologiyalar" nashriyoti, 2008.
3. Ahrorova Z. O'qitishning yangicha usullari. // Ta'lim va tarbiya, 2003 yil 3-4- sonlari.
4. Artikova, M. (2021). DEMAND FOR A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH TO THE ACTIVITIES OF TEACHERS IN MODERN CONDITIONS. InterConf.
5. Artikova, M. B. (2019). EXPERIENCE IN DEVELOPING ENTREPRENEURSHIP SKILLS IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 1(7), 250-255.
6. Mirzayev, O. K. (2024). HISTORICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE FORMATION OF ELEMENTARY ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS OF CHILDREN IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION. Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal, 5(02), 167-171.
7. Xusanovich, M. O. (2021). Formation of Elements of Entrepreneurial Activity In Pupils Of The Preschool Educational Organization. JournalNX, 1, 265.
8. Mirzaev, O. (2022). The role of ethics and aesthetics in the formation of entrepreneurial relations between individuals. Science and innovation, 1(B6), 125-130.